

Percentage of Tertiary Enrollment in the Global Innovation Index

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Tertiary enrollment, expressed as a gross percentage, measures the level of participation in higher education within a given country. This indicator accounts for the total number of students enrolled in tertiary education programs, regardless of their age, as a percentage of the population at the theoretical age for attending university or equivalent institutions. The gross percentage provides a comprehensive view of the accessibility and expansion of higher education systems, including both young individuals attending education on schedule and adults returning to their studies. While a high percentage indicates broad participation, it may also reflect a high number of students who are behind schedule or older individuals pursuing further education. Conversely, low percentages may signal challenges in accessing tertiary education, such as economic, infrastructural, or other barriers. This indicator is crucial for analyzing a country's capacity to train a qualified workforce, contributing to socioeconomic development and innovation. The data cover the period from 2013 to 2022.

Percentage of Tertiary Enrollment in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on tertiary enrollment in 2022 reveal a highly varied global landscape, reflecting deep differences in educational systems, political priorities, and economic conditions across countries. At the top of the rankings is Greece, with a gross enrollment percentage of 100%, indicative of particularly broad access to higher education. Following are countries like Turkey (76.8%) and Australia (76.2%), which demonstrate significant participation in tertiary education, often linked to national strategies aimed at promoting access and enhancing the quality of their educational systems. Among Nordic and European nations, Finland (61.5%), Spain (61.5%), and the Netherlands (57.5%) stand out for achieving a balance between educational quality and accessibility, reflecting established traditions of investment in education. However, not all developed countries show such high rates: for instance, the United Kingdom records 42.7%, and Italy reaches only 42.9%, highlighting challenges in ensuring broad access to higher education compared to other European nations. The United States (58%) maintains an intermediate position, although lower than expected given the scale and resources of its educational system. Asian countries like Singapore (60.2%) and South Korea (65.3%) reaffirm their commitment to education as a driver of innovation, while China's more modest 37.6% signals the need for further efforts to broaden access. The situation is even more critical in low- and middle-income countries, where enrollment percentages are significantly lower. In Sub-Saharan Africa, many countries report values below 10%, such as Kenya (4.1%), Mozambique (2.2%), and Uganda (0.7%). These figures reflect structural challenges such as lack of resources, inadequate infrastructure, and economic barriers that limit access to higher education for large segments of the population. Similarly, in South and Southeast Asia, countries like Nepal (6.5%) and Pakistan (5.6%) face comparable difficulties, underscoring the urgency of more inclusive policies and targeted investments. In Latin America, disparities are evident: countries like Argentina (63.2%) and Chile (61.6%) show significant progress, while others such as Guatemala (12.5%) and Honduras (14.8%) struggle to ensure broader access. The presence of countries like Paraguay with zero reported enrollment underscores the severity of specific situations, which may stem from either a lack of data or particularly severe systemic challenges.

Percentage of Tertiary Enrollment in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022. The analysis of tertiary enrollment data from 2013 to 2022 reveals significant global variability, with some countries achieving remarkable progress and others experiencing dramatic declines. Among the countries with the most significant improvements, Botswana (+133.85%) and Morocco (+109.09%) stand out, having doubled or more their enrollment rates, likely due to targeted policies aimed at expanding access to higher education and improving educational infrastructure. Tanzania (+100%) and Kuwait (+91.75%) follow with notable growth, reflecting an increasing focus on higher education as a tool for economic and social development. Nations such as Namibia (+72.5%) and Georgia (+51.93%) also show significant, though more moderate, progress. China (+48.03%) and Brazil (+45.27%) have consolidated their roles as emerging powers in tertiary education, while Turkey (+43.82%) and Bahrain (+37.46%) demonstrate considerable expansion despite their already strong educational foundations. On the other hand, the data also highlight worrying cases of decline. Among these are significant drops in advanced countries such as South Korea (-34.7%), Slovenia (-41.13%), and the United States (-36.89%), where the decreases likely reflect factors such as demographic decline, reduced priority for tertiary education, or more complex access due to high costs. In Europe, countries like Romania (-42.33%), Hungary (-42.74%), and Slovakia (-44.51%) have recorded substantial losses, suggesting difficulties in maintaining competitiveness in an increasingly demanding global context. Dramatic situations are also observed in low-income countries such as Mali (-80.77%), Guinea (-80.39%), and Uganda (-91.36%), where the collapse of higher education reflects deep economic, social, and infrastructural crises.

Conclusions. On average, the percentage of tertiary enrollment decreased by 16.90%, dropping from 37.93 units to 31.52 units between 2013 and 2022. The top performers are Botswana (+133.85%), Morocco (+109.09%), Tanzania (+100%), Kuwait (+91.75%), and Namibia (+72.5%). The worst performers are Niger (-71.43%), Rwanda (-73.68%), Guinea (-80.39%), Mali (-80.77%), and Uganda (-91.36%).

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Performanace	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Botswana	6,5	15,2	8,7	133,85
	Morocco	12,1	25,3	13,2	109,09
	Tanzania	1,3	2,6	1,3	100
	Kuwait	20,6	39,5	18,9	91,75
	Namibia	8	13,8	5,8	72,5
Worse Performers	Niger	0,7	0,2	-0,5	-71,43
	Rwanda	5,7	1,5	-4,2	-73,68
	Guinea	10,2	2	-8,2	-80,39
	Mali	5,2	1	-4,2	-80,77
	Uganda	8,1	0,7	-7,4	-91,36